

GARLIC WITHOUT ODOR: NEW OPPORTUNITIES FOR IMMUNE ENHANCEMENT

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Relevance: Garlic is one of the most extensively studied natural immunomodulators with antibacterial, antiviral, and antioxidant activity. Its use is limited by the presence of a characteristic unpleasant odor associated with sulfur-containing compounds. To reduce the odor, we used cherry, as it is rich in polyphenols, organic acids, and antioxidants, which are able to neutralize volatile garlic compounds while preserving its beneficial properties. This makes the topic relevant for both pharmaceuticals and the food industry.

Objective of the study: To investigate the possibilities of preserving the immunomodulatory properties of garlic while eliminating its characteristic odor.

Materials and methods: Fresh garlic and cherry fruits were used for the study. Garlic samples were treated with freshly squeezed cherry juice and cherry extract.

Polyphenols and flavonoids (quercetin, anthocyanins) bound volatile sulfur compounds of garlic, reducing their volatility and odor intensity.

Organic acids (malic, citric, succinic) neutralized sulfur compounds and altered the pH of the medium, reducing odor spread.

Antioxidants (vitamin C, anthocyanins) slowed the decomposition of allicin, preventing the formation of a pungent odor.

Enzymatic compounds of cherry contributed to the degradation of sulfur metabolites in the oral cavity, providing a deodorizing effect.

Odor reduction was evaluated organoleptically and by gas chromatography based on the content of volatile compounds. Biological activity was assessed by measuring antioxidant activity and immunomodulatory effects (phagocyte activity and cytokine levels in vitro).

Results: Treatment of garlic with cherry extract significantly reduced the concentration of allyl methyl sulfide and diallyl disulfide. The antioxidant activity of garlic was preserved and, in some cases, enhanced due to cherry polyphenols. The immunomodulatory effect of garlic remained at the level of fresh raw material.

Conclusions:

1. Cherry effectively reduces the intensity of garlic odor through the interaction of its polyphenols, organic acids, and antioxidants with volatile sulfur compounds.

2. At the same time, the beneficial properties of garlic (immunomodulatory and antimicrobial activity) are preserved.

3. The combined use of garlic and cherry is promising for the development of deodorized phytopreparations and functional food products.